

Android malware detection using GIST based machine learning and deep learning techniques

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ABSTRACT

In today's digital world, Android phones play a vital part in a variety of facets of both professionals and individuals' personal and professional lives. Android phones are great for getting things done faster and more organized. The proportionate increase in the number of malicious applications has also been seen to be expanding. Since the play store offers millions of apps, detection of malware apps is challenging task. In this paper, a methodology is introduced for detecting malware in Android applications through the utilization of global image shape transform (GIST) features extracted from grayscale images of the applications. The dataset comprises samples of both malware and benign apps collected from the virus share website. After converting the apps into grayscale images, GIST features are extracted to capture their global spatial layout. Various machine learning (ML) algorithms, such as logistic regression (LR), k-nearest neighbour (KNN), AdaBoost, decision tree (DT), Naïve Bayes (NB), random forest (RF), support vector machine (SVM), extra tree classifier (ETC), and gradient boosting (GB), are employed to classify the applications according to their GIST features. Furthermore, a feed forward neural network (FFNN) is utilized as a deep learning (DL) technique to further improve the accuracy of classification. The performance of each algorithm is evaluated using metrics such as accuracy, precision and recall. The results demonstrated that the FFNN achieves superior accuracy compared to traditional ML classifiers, indicating its effectiveness in detecting malware in Android apps.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of mobile devices, particularly those running the Android operating system (OS), has led to a surge in the development and distribution of mobile applications. While this has brought about immense convenience and innovation, it has also opened the door to various security threats, including the proliferation of malware targeting Android apps. Malicious software, or malware, poses significant risks to users, ranging from data theft and financial fraud to device compromise and privacy breaches.

To address the growing concern of malware in Android apps, extensive research efforts have been devoted to developing effective detection methods. Traditional approaches typically rely on static and dynamic analysis techniques, which often require access to the app's executable code or runtime behavior. However, these methods may be limited by their dependence on specific app features or behaviors, making them susceptible to evasion tactics employed by sophisticated malware variants.

In this work, a novel method was proposed for detecting malware in Android apps by utilizing global image shape transform (GIST) features extracted from grayscale images of the app's user interface. The approach offered several advantages over traditional techniques, including the ability to analyze apps without requiring access to their executable code or runtime behavior. By representing apps as grayscale images and extracting GIST features to capture their global spatial layout, the aim was to provide a robust and versatile framework for malware detection.

Roy *et al.* [1] presented an Android malware detection technique using supervised learning. The method detected malicious application programming interface (API) calls and unusual behaviors, offering insights for researchers and users while suggesting avenues for future Android system technologies. Chowdhury *et al.* [2] highlighted the rising threat of Android malware to mobile device security and data integrity. Machine learning (ML) approaches for Android malware detection were tested, discussing security and malware issues on the platform. Later, they explored supervised, unsupervised, and ML detection methods and compared their effectiveness, assessing metrics. The evaluation revealed method flaws and suggested further research. It provided a detailed overview of Android malware detection using ML and its historical context. Awais *et al.* [3] used ANTI-ANT method to identify and prevent mobile malware. They targeted Botnets, Rootkits, SMS malware, Spywares, app installers, and ransomware. Three detection layers application, user background, and package formed the foundation. The extraction and categorization of features employed static and dynamic studies. One-shot learning-based Siamese neural networks were developed to recognize and categorize malware attacks [4]. It tested the strategy on 9,470 benign and 5,550 malware apps from Drebin. Several steps like pre-processing, data splitting, model architecture, training, and assessment done and reported good results.

A static feature-based ML model for Android malware detection was presented in [5]. It extracted features from a fresh dataset of co-existing permissions and API requests at different combination levels using the FP-growth method. The model was accurate using multiple ML techniques, including random forest (RF) employing permissions features at the second combination level. Alamro *et al.* [6] introduced the ensemble technique for automated Android malware detection using an optimal algorithm approach. They employed data preprocessing and an ensemble of three ML models, support vector machine (SVM), KELM, and neural networks. Parameter tuning was done resulting in improved detection. Rule-based and ML-based specific-type detectors were used to detect Android malware before and after installation [7]. It was non-invasive and obtained application functionalities without breaching licensing. Experiments on an Android smartphone showed the solution was three times quicker and used ten times less CPU, saving energy. It had much greater balanced accuracy, nine times less false positives, and ten times fewer false negatives than state-of-the-art systems. Banik and Singh [8] introduced a novel Android malware detection method using genuine Android permissions. They reverse-engineered APKs to extract genuine permission features and utilized frequent pattern growth to identify common permission combinations. These pairs were then inputted into a multi-layered neural network model and five traditional ML models for comparison. Evaluation metrics showed over 96% accuracy on both the Drebin dataset and a custom dataset from the past five years.

Mahindru *et al.* [9] introduced "YarowskyDroid," a technique for identifying malware-infected apps using semi-supervised ML and federated learning. Apps were installed locally on users' smartphones for privacy protection. Information from users improved the malware detection algorithm. The study addressed users' inability to detect malware in downloaded apps by proposing a semi-supervised learning technique. Lakshmanarao and Shashi [10] extracted opcodes from Android apps and applied recurrent neural network (RNN) for malware detection. The long short-term memory (LSTM) variant of RNN used in the experiment and reported good detection rate. Subash *et al.* [11] used static permissions and ML to identify Android malware. They performed API analysis on 400 Android apps to identify malicious activity. Later, trained and compared three ML algorithms after preprocessing. Sharma and Babbar [12] detected internet of things (IoT) Android malware using ML. This approach builds an ML model from Android malware samples and excellent applications. IoT malware detection uses ML methods including Naïve Bayes (NB), k-nearest neighbour (KNN), decision tree (DT), and RF on the Android Malware dataset and reported good results. Shatnawi *et al.* [13] proposed a static base classification technique for malware detection based on Android permissions and API calls to strengthen malware detection efforts. A large new Android malware dataset (CICInvesAndMal2019) was used with three popular ML algorithms: SVM, KNN, and NB.

Droos *et al.* [14] proposed ML classifiers for malware detection. To maximize detection accuracy, the algorithm used a feature set from the CICMalDroid2020 dataset to classify each APK as malicious or legal. Results showed that RF was the most accurate ML classifier. Bandi and Sherpa [15] detected

CICAndMal2017 Android malware using ML. Feature engineering was used to find the most important characteristics from a balanced dataset extracted by random sampling. The balanced dataset with specified characteristics trains ML algorithms. All models were first trained using ‘Label’ and subsequently ‘Family’. Both examples used RF to get 99% accuracy. Alkahtani and Aldhyani [16] proposed ML techniques for malware detection. Several ML and DL algorithms applied and achieved good detection rate. Lakshmanarao and Shashi [17] applied ensemble learning for malware detection. Two types of ensembles stacking and blending applied and achieved accuracy of more than 95%. Kanchhal and Murugaanandam [18] built and injected Android malware onto an Android device or emulator, hiding it from the victim. The victim system provided vital data. Additionally, RF, ML discovered the virus. Alani and Awad [19] developed an explainable ML based lightweight Android malware detection method. To distinguish harmful and benign malware, the suggested approach used application characteristics. Over 98% accuracy was achieved with a tiny device footprint in testing. It was also described through shapley additive explanation (SHAP) values.

Ban *et al.* [20] explored how string properties like malware’s security-sensitive APIs affected the deep learning (DL) based family analysis model. Testing on a 2018–2020 malware dataset classified by behavior indicated that combined characteristics achieved good accuracy. The malware detection approach by Cilleruelo *et al.* [21] used application static analysis and innovative training and dataset building. Google Play application lifespans were used to create a new dataset to prevent antivirus engine biases. The novel detecting mechanism differed from prior engines. Using 91,000 Google Play Store apps, experimental findings indicated 90% accuracy. Li *et al.* [22] suggested a factorization machine-based Android malware classifier that extracts features from manifest files and source code. Precision was high on the DREBIN dataset. Zhou *et al.* [23] suggested a static SIMGRU-based Android malware detection solution. It enhanced the gated recurrent unit (GRU) with similarities, creating new structures. These structures fared better than GRU models and other approaches in experiments. Alswaina and Elleithy [24] created RevEng, which provided application rights to ML algorithms. They used heavily randomized trees to decrease permissions, improving accuracy and execution speed. Two permission representation methods were tested: binary and weighted depending on feature relevance. Kumar *et al.* [25] described a malware detection system using ML, DL, and behavior and signature-based methodologies. It identified detection issues, classified ML methods, studied fundamental tactics, and examined DL. The RF model outperformed five other methods with good accuracy.

2. METHOD

Figure 1 depicts malware detection methodology used in this paper. This work contributed to the ongoing efforts to combat malware threats in the Android ecosystem by introducing a novel approach that leveraged image-based feature representations and ML algorithms. Through experimental evaluation and comparative analysis, the effectiveness of the method was demonstrated in accurately identifying malicious apps and mitigating the risks associated with mobile malware. The dataset used in this work consists of samples of both malware and benign apps collected from the virus share website, ensuring a diverse and representative set of app samples for analysis. After preprocessing the apps and extracting GIST features, a range of ML algorithms, including logistic regression (LR), KNN, AdaBoost, DT, NB, RF, SVM, extra tree classifier (ETC), and gradient boosting (GB), were applied to classify the apps based on their feature representations.

2.1. Android apps collection

Malicious mobile applications were gathered from virusshare.com. Malware apps are collected from two different datasets in virusshare namely vs2012 and vs2016. The number of malware samples in both datasets are 2,000 and 2,000 respectively. For benign applications; 1,700 samples were collected from CICAndMal2017 [26], while an additional 300 benign applications were sourced from the Google Play Store. With these apps, two datasets created each with 2,000 malware and 2,000 benign apps.

2.2. App to image conversion

Android apps are typically zipped files with .apk extension. Grayscale images were created in two ways: directly converting apk files and extracting dex files from apk files to generate grayscale images. The procedure involves opening a directory with APK/DEX files. For each file, the size is calculated. Depending on the size, the width of the image is determined (ranging from 32 to 1024). The file is then converted into an image using Python NumPy’s “fromfile” method and saved as a .png file with the determined width using the “imsave” method. Finally, the directory is closed. This process applied in two different settings. In first case, the entire Android apps are converted to images. In second case, only dex files of apps are converted to images.

Figure 1. Proposed method

2.3. Extracting GIST features

The GIST descriptor, which is based on wavelet decomposition of an image, was utilized to compute texture features from the grayscale images. The extraction process was shown in Figure 2. This feature has been successful in scene classification and object classification. GIST global descriptors are useful for comparing images based on their content. After creating grayscale images for all malware and benign files, GIST features are extracted from images. The GIST features, typically employed in categorizing scenes such as forests, streets, and mountains, were adapted for use with Android APK files. The local representation of the image is then given by: $v_L(x) = v_k(x) | k=1 \dots N$, here N is the number of sub-bands (N=20 taken). For the extraction of GIST descriptor texture features from the grayscale images, the Python “pyleargist” package was utilized. First 320 texture features for all the images are extracted and these feature vectors are converted to csv files.

Figure 2. GIST descriptor feature extraction

Algorithm 1 applied to Android apps collected including malware and benign apps. After applying Algorithm 1, two csv datasets created one with vs2012 malware samples and another with malware vs2016 samples. In both thr dataset, same benign samples are used.

Algorithm 1. Extraction of GIST features from gray scale images

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Step 1: Open directory with gray-scale images
Step 2: For all the files in the directory:
Step 2.1: X = numpy.zeros((sum(no_of_imgs), 320))
           #Feature Matrix with 320 features
Step 2.2: i = 0
Step 2.3: Open all images with .png extension
Step 2.4: Apply python leargist package
Step 2.5: X[i]= des [0:320], i=i+1
Step 2.6: Convert X to data frame and then convert it in to csv file
Step 3: Close the directory
    
```

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After extracting GIST features from Android APKs, a range of linear ML classification algorithms was employed for malware detection. Subsequently, a DL feed-forward neural network algorithm was also utilized. Evaluation encompassed both ML and DL algorithms using varying numbers of samples of malware and benignware APKs. While linear ML algorithms achieved an accuracy of over 96%, the DL algorithm demonstrated consistent accuracy and recall rate across all experiments. These experiments were conducted using two different setups. In the first method, the GIST features of the entire APK images were utilized, whereas in the second case, only the image features of the DEX files were considered. In both cases feed forward neural network outperforms linear classification techniques.

3.1. Apply ML and DL algorithms with dataset1 (whole apk image to GIST feature dataset)

In this step, several ML classifiers applied with whole apk image to GIST dataset and the results are shown in Table 1. In Table 1, P indicates precision, R indicates recall and A indicates accuracy. From Table 1, it is observed that FFNN and RF given 99%, 90% highest accuracy rate with good precision and recall rate for the two datasets. Next, GB, ETC, and Adaboost performed well with good accuracy.

Table 1. Results with ML algorithms (whole apk taken as grayscale image)

Algorithm	Dataset1-A (malware: 2,000 from VS-2012, Benign:2,000)			Dataset1-B (malware:2,000 (from VS-2016, Benign: 2,000)		
	P	R	A	P	R	A
LR	97	91	95	91	60	80
K-NN	95	94	95	90	70	83
AdaBoost	98	95	97	84	68	80
DT	97	95	96	76	72	77
NB	99	86	93	83	67	81
RF	98	96	98	87	77	85
SVM	100	86	93	85	50	75
ETC	98	95	97	89	74	85
GB	99	95	97	76	77	80
FFNN	97	99	98	88	92	90

For dataset-1A and dataset-1B, a FFNN with the configuration in Figure 3 achieved better results. It has one input layer, 2 hidden layers, and one output layer. The number of neurons in each layer was 160, 81, 42, and 1 respectively. A batch size of 5 and 250 epochs were considered for training. Dropout, a method utilized to prevent overfitting, was implemented by adding one dropout layer to the model. This configuration resulted in a recall of 99% and an accuracy of 98% for dataset-1A and recall of 92% and accuracy of 90% for dataset-1B.

Figure 3. Feed forward neural network model (apk files as gray scale images)

3.2. Apply ML and DL algorithms with dataset2 (apk dex image to GIST feature dataset)

In this step, several ML classifiers applied with apk dex image to GIST dataset and the results are shown in Table 2. From Table 2, it is observed that FFNN given 98.7% and 98.8% highest accuracies with dataset2-A and dataset2-B. The precision and recall also good for FFNN. Next RF performed well with 98%, 98% for dataset2-A and dataset2-B.

For these datasets, a feed forward neural network with the configuration in Figure 4 achieved superior results. It has one input layer, three hidden layers, and one output layer. The number of neurons in each layer was 160, 80, 40, 21, and 1 respectively. A batch size of 6 and 250 epochs were considered for training. Additionally, one dropout layer was added to the model.

Table 2. Results with various ML algorithms (apk dex file taken as grayscale image)

Algorithm	Dataset2-A (malware: 2,000 from VS-2012, Benign:2,000)			Dataset2-B (malware: 2,000 from VS-2012, Benign:2,000)		
	P	R	A	P	R	A
LR	97	94	95.9	97	93	95.9
K-NN	95	98	97	97	99	97.9
AdaBoost	96	99	97.7	98	98	97.5
DT	94	99	97	95	98	96.6
NB	97	93	95.5	98	94	96
RF	97	99	98	97	99	98
SVM	98	92	98.5	96	98	96.8
ETC	98	99	98.5	97	98	97.9
GB	98	93	95.9	97	98	97.6
FFNN	93	100	98.7	99	99	98.8

Figure 4. FFNN model (dex files as gray scale images)

3.3. Proposed methodology performance evaluation

Table 3 and Figure 5 shows performance comparison of proposed method with existing works. In comparison with existing methods, the proposed GIST-based approach demonstrates superior performance in malware detection accuracy. Conventional ML methods [1] achieve a respectable accuracy of 97%, providing a solid baseline for evaluation. SVM [3], another widely used technique, performs slightly lower with an accuracy of 96.6%. Odat and Yaseen [5], RF achieved a competitive accuracy of 98%. In the proposed method, the FFNN with whole image dataset given good accuracy of 98%. However, the proposed GIST-based approach for lex image dataset with FNN technique outperformed all existing methods, achieving an impressive accuracy of 98.8%. This substantial improvement signifies the efficacy of the GIST-based approach in enhancing accuracy in malware detection tasks.

Table 3. Comparison with existing work

Model	Accuracy
Conventional ML [1]	97%
SVM [3]	96.6%
RF [5]	98%
Proposed GIST based approach (lex images dataset)	98%
Proposed GIST based approach (whole apk images dataset)	98.8%

Figure 5. Performance evaluation of proposed model

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper addresses the growing concern of malware presence in Android apps, given the significant role these devices play in both personal and professional spheres. With millions of apps available on the Play Store, detecting malicious software presents a formidable challenge. The proposed method leverages GIST features extracted from grayscale images of Android apps, providing a unique approach to malware detection. By employing various ML algorithms and a FFNN, superior accuracy was attained in classifying apps based on their features. The FFNN, in particular, demonstrated effectiveness in detecting malware compared to traditional classifiers. Overall, the proposed method offers a robust framework for enhancing Android security, empowering users to identify and mitigate potential threats effectively. Future work involves exploring scalability and efficiency to handle the growing volume of Android apps. Additionally, integrating real-time threat intelligence and behavioral analysis techniques aims to enhance malware detection accuracy and effectiveness on Android devices.

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